

DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITION

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ABSTRACT

The paper explains cohesive and organizational structure of texts. It is restricted to the description, identifications and analysis of written English composition. The essays analyzed span over narrative so as to determine the extent in which vocabulary, style and grammatical structures aid in text formation. Generally, all the essays analyzed in this paper are coherent and cohesive, but lack a variety of cohesive innovation.

KEYWORDS: Discourse analysis, cohesion, style, grammatical structures, organizational structures and vocabulary

INTRODUCTION

Writing is a very difficult task especially to second language learners whose L1 employs different, or does not have an orthography.

The real difficulty could be associated with the circumstances in which written communication takes place, and the social purposes it serves are not the same. From narrow linguistic viewpoint, it is possible to say that writing is written speech. But if language is considered from social standpoint, it makes no sense at all to assume that written language shares the same characteristics with its spoken variant.

Writing is therefore a social activity of a rather specialist and restricted kind, so to learn how to write is to learn a kind of social behaviour that is a rare one. Most people do little, or no writing at all. Even those who do writing, do so as part of their professional activity. When one considers the matter, most educator lawyers, journalists, businessmen, and civil servants and students are regular writers, but brick-layers, drivers, farmer, electricians, factory-workers, etc are not.

In all societies whether developed, or developing, it is a truism to say that the latter group of people are in the majority. This explains why it is a fact to say that writing is an activity of the minority-the literate ones.

Discourse analysis is widely identified as one of the most far-reaching, but least defined areas in linguistics. The reason being that it has often been defined into two distinct ways: as a unit of language that is larger than the sentence, and as the general use of language. The first one views regularities governing texts, while the latter focuses on social function of speaking.

This paper is an attempt to analyze written discourse of two hundred level English students' writing of Gombe State University from cohesive perspective.

Text is the verbal record of a communicative event (Brown and Yule (1983:199). A number of authors are concerned with how text is formed, for example, Dijk 1972; Beaugrande 1980; Beaugrande and Dressler 1981; Halliday and Hasan 1976). Halliday and Hasan (1976) distinguish between a text and a non-text. A text depends on cohesive relationships both within and between sentences, and beyond. This statement is supported by an example of a piece of utterance from Halliday and Hasan (1976:2).

- (1) Wash and core six cooking apples.
- (2) Put them into a fireproof dish.

From the above it is obvious that 'them' in the second clause refers back to the apples (anaphoric). This anaphoric function creates cohesive to the two clauses. So, the two are perceived as a whole.

But, discourse analysts like Brown and Yule (1983) argue that the use of 'them' exemplified above may not refer to the 'six cooking apples'. The argument here is that the six cooking apples might have gone a process of change because of the cooking, unlike when the apples are fresh as they are referred to in the first clause. Brown and Yule (1981:4) present a similar illustration:

Kill an active, plump chicken.

Prepare it for the oven, cut it into four pieces and roast it with thyme for one hour.

From the above, 'it' used in the second clause refers to the chicken in the first clause, but it is argued that a reader who substituted the word 'chicken' with 'it' has failed to understand and interpret the text because, like the 'apples', the chicken has undergone metamorphosis. Halliday and Hasan (1976) cohesive model fails to account for how text is understood. They are rather concerned with those linguistic elements that the speaker/writer uses to create relationships.

Cohesion is another term that is used in this paper to refer placing of one point of view, one attitude, one tense, appropriate traditional words, correct pronouns and their antecedents to link linguistic items together. Discourse is said to be connected if only all the sentences contribute to the expression. In this case, it is fair to say that unity is a property of the sentence, paragraph and discourse at large. Incoherence on the other hand is achieved when a writer uses irrelevant materials to a central idea. Problems arise when many readers are faced with the task of understanding how texts are organized. The main challenge is how to distinguish between main and subordinating ideas. This category of text users fail to realize that main ideas are primary points closely connected and amplified by subordinating details.

Every sentence produced whether written or spoken is aimed at expressing an idea. The idea is formed through a collection of varieties of interrelated words structured in such a way that the rules of the language and style of the language user are not jeopardized. But unfortunately, some second language users of English, in an attempt to achieve this, render a piece of language weak and vague.

Theoretical framework

The model propose in this research is that of Halliday and Hasan (1976). The model stipulates, or identifies five major categories of which the concept cohesion is built. These include: reference, substitution, ellipsis, conjunction and lexical cohesion.

Substitution is a device which aids cohesion. The relation that is expressed is that of wording rather than meaning. It is a counter which is used for the avoidance of repetition of lexical items. It operates at three levels.

Types of substitution

1. Nominal: one, ones, same
 2. Verbal: do
 3. Clausal: so, not
1. Nominal substitution functions as the head of a nominal group and can be substituted by items which are themselves heads of nominal groups. However, not every occurrence of 'one' is substitutable, for example, the generic 'one', cardinal or numeral 'one', as in:
One should always keep quite (generic)
He made one terrible mistake (numeral). The one with cohesive force is the nominal 'one'. 'The one he likes most is his father' (nominal).
 2. Verbal substitution contains 'do'. It operates as head of a verbal group, in the position of the lexical verb and it takes the final position within the verbal group structure. E.g, Do you eat snakes? 'Yes' I do (eat snakes).
 3. Clausal substitution is a replacement of the entire linguistic items in a clause, and the substitution are: 'so', not.
'The man must be an immigrant from Togo'.
'I think so'.

'Has the weather changed?' 'I hope not'. Another form of cohesion is achieved by reference. Reference refers to speech situation through the category of persons. These are:

- (i) Personal reference: 'I' only the speaker 'you' refers to the addressee, 'we' includes both the speaker and other persons: 'he/him'; 'she/her' and 'it'.
- (ii) Demonstrative reference: This refers to reference made by means of location usually on a scale of proximity and the items that refer here include: 'this', 'these' and 'those'.
- (iii) Comparative reference: As the name implies, reference compares similar or dissimilar things. Comparative elements may be expressed in terms of quality, quantity, or even in an implied form, as in, 'the government may take tighter measure'. Reference items can be anaphoric or cataphoric. E.g, The cat died yesterday. It was buried this morning (anaphoric). He who speaks English comes from England. (He) cataphoric. On the other hand, an item can be exophoric if it does not signal that information should be retrieved in the textual world, rather, such an information is a context-base. The essential point in understanding reference whether endophoric (anaphoric or cataphoric) or exophoric (textual) is that there is a presupposition that must be satisfied; and the object which the speaker/writer refers to must be retrievable somehow. Some of the reference materials include: personal pronouns, possessive, determiners, possessive adjectives.

English recognize the speaker 'I' and addressee 'you', with no distinction to the number of addressees. However, 'we' stands for the speaker with other person or without addressee. Also, the grammar of English provides a generalized form with human referent 'one'. E.g, 'what this government did is capable of discouraging one'.

The use of persons plays a great role in that they refer to relevant, persons and objects. E.g, if a sentence begins: 'Musa speaks good English'. It may have multiple anaphoric reference: 'he', 'his', 'him' which stand for 'Musa'.

Ellipses is defined as sharing of structural component between clauses and a typical example is anaphoric ie the complete structure occurs before the ellipsis. Ellipses allow the omission of some structural components provided that version is recoverable. For: instance,
'They were married in 1970, divorced in 1975, and reconciled 2000. 'They' is ellipted in the second and third part of the sentence, and 'in' in the last part of the sentence.

Beaugrande and Dressler (1981) advise that utilizing texts with no ellipses consumes time, space and energy. However, they argue that excessive use of ellipsis may demand intensive search. The text producers must weigh the appropriateness of ellipsis so as to avoid mistaken identity of linguistic items that create cohesion. Ellipsis operates at three levels:

- (1) Ellipsis of the clausal level is related to question-answer process in dialogue and it consists of (a) Yes/No ellipsis, and (b) WH-element ellipsis. E.g, 'Have you eaten the food?' 'yes'. (I have eaten the food). This is a typical example of a dialogue. In a WH-question, the entire clause is omitted except for the WH itself. 'You have to study hard' 'why?' (Should I study hard).
- (2) The verbal group ellipsis explains the kind of omission that takes place at the level of the verbal group. E.g, 'Have you been to London?' No.
- (3) Nominal group ellipsis omits the elements within the nominal group. E.g, feel? 'How do you feel now?' 'Great!' (I feel great).
- (4) Conjunctions link linguistic items which the speaker is understood to be assuming some kind of relation between two things.

Below is a list of the devices that can signal relationship among event or situations.

1. Conjunction links things which have the same status in which both are true in the textual world.
2. Disjunction connects things which have alternative status, two of which only one can be true in the textual world.
3. Subordination joins things when the status of one depends on that of other.

5. Lexical cohesion:

These are lexical items such as: synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, repetition and collocation. Synonymy is the term used to explain the linguistic relatedness of similar items or lexemes. Palmer(1996:85) provides a list of synonymous words such as: statement/political; hide/conceal; liberty/freedom; free/relaxed; lonely/solitary; direct/control. Though these words are synonymous, it is indeed impossible in English to have absolute synonyms. All that is required of English users is appropriate contextual use of linguistics items.

Antonym – is oppositeness in meaning and it can be used within and across sentence to foster unity semantically. E.g, ‘we sought for war, peace was gotten’. Other forms of antonyms include complementary words such as: male/female; obedient/disobedient; open/shut, etc.

Another form of antonyms is gradable. The degree of the gradability is shown using the morphemes, er, est and their periphrastic variants, more, most. Gradable antonyms can be marked if they reflect features of measurement, as in, less intelligent, richer, etc. while unmarked antonyms do not possess any of the feature mentioned above, as in, ‘the boy has a high sense of reasoning.

Hyponymy: Linguistic relations of hyponymy indicates that there is a super ordinate item either includes, or entails subordinate, or much smaller item (co-hyponyms). E.g, Peugeot, Nissan, Honda are co-hyponyms of the super ordinate, automobile. Collocation is a relatedness in meaning between lexical items where independent words co-occur with one another and they all function in a similar semantic environment. A collocation involves the use of word which are distinct but are brought together based on the syntax and the grammar of the language. E.g, ‘exceptional child’, ‘flock of sheep’, herd of cows’, ‘pride of lion’. Bound collocations refers to words which are used in a restricted sense and context. They include: proverbs and idioms. E.g, ‘All work no play makes Jack a dull boy’. ‘The man has kicked the bucket’. Any attempt to insert a contrary word may render the idiom meaningless. In other words, bound collocations do not have substitutes.

Finally, repetition of the same lexical items may also enhance unity but care must be taken to avoid excessive.

Discourse Analysis in Written Composition

Students’ composition have been used to asses the writing skill. It enables students the opportunities to view their own production somewhat in objective manners. Elements which enhance good composition such as logical progression of ideas, the use of appropriate transitions, limiting and supporting the topic are all features that students recognize when their essay are assessed and given back to them.

Many researches have been carried out on the cohesiveness of students writing and its overall quality of its coherence. For example, Witte and Faigley (1981) conduct a research on a relationship between coherence and cohesion in college students’ writing, and discover that there is a clear relationship between coherence and cohesion. In a related vein, Fitzgerald and Spiegel (1986) examine the relationship between coherence and cohesion in third and six grade students’ writing. The result shows a clear variation between coherence and cohesion in terms of text content. Similarly, Anderson (1980) uses cohesive frequency to assess students’ written language samples holistically by a variety of cohesive forms. The finding indicates that there is a high degree of cohesive inconsistency in the language samples. Cummins 1989) carry out a research in which a good performance of L2 learners in the area of discourse coherence is attributable to their ability to transfers discourse competence already gained in their L1.

METHODOLOGY

The research comprises of essays written by two hundred level English students of Gombe State University. All the essays are written in April 9th 2008 a total of twenty three essay scripts are assessed and analyzed, using clear instructions. The essays are those written in normal classroom situation with its usual mixture of readiness and anxiety, within or without proof-reading.

Each discourse is split into numbered excerpts so as to show the kind of ties. This is because analysis of text from cohesive perspective revolves around ties, for this reason, it is pertinent to say that the relationship is directional: anaphora. Or cataphora. This helps to explain the data clearly. For the reason of space, only a few examples are presented. To avoid repetitions of data presentation, the same cohesive occurrence are not shown in this paper.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

ESSAY 1

Excerpt 1: I (name withheld) leaving at Tudun Wada, Kasuwan Mata, Gombe, Gombe State witnessed the fight between the two armed robbers yesterday, and the cause of the fight was that both of them are arguing whether or not to kill the woman along side the child.

Excerpt 2: The woman was their neighbour, but they robbed her at the highway and she recognized them when returned back home, they were afraid of being exposed; the first one insisted that they should kill the woman and her child because she would have told the child what happened.

Comment: The introduction is wrong and vague because of mindless use of the definite article 'the' to refer 'fight' and 'woman'. There have to be preceding details about the two nouns before the use of the article. As it is there no cohesive force to link the message presented. However, the use of 'the woman' in the second excerpt is appropriate, but for what has been explained above, the reader is forced to imagine that 'the woman' has an anaphoric reference to what would have been 'a woman' in the preceding arrangement. Other elements that create cohesion in the second excerpt include: 'their', 'they' and 'them' and in the second excerpt make anaphoric to the robbers in the first excerpt. Similarly, 'she', and 'her' are pronouns variants that have semantic values in identifying their referent, 'the woman'. 'One' which is mentioned twice in the second excerpt is a nominal substitution referring to one robber. This device plays a great role in creating a link between certain elements of the two excerpts.

The use of 'I' to begin a statement before its antecedent is a cataphoric reference. In this essay, the writer begins, I (name withheld) to point forward to his name. The reader/hearer finds no difficulty in relating the pronoun and its referent.

ESSAY 2

Excerpt 1: To witness an event like this one is not what we wish for, but even though I witnessed it, I am glad I survived it and I do not wish any one to partake in this.

Excerpt 2: It was a sunny Sunday in Garki, Area II, Abuja, I was sleeping after just returning from church and tired. I heard voices of two people arguing, and I heard what seemed to be the cause of the argument was money.

Comment: 'This' used in excerpt 1 is a circumstantial demonstrative reference, referring to where the speaker is. 'We' also used in the excerpt is an exophoric reference. It does not occur in the textual world. Therefore, it is not cohesive. The reader/hearer must search for the referent outside the text. 'We', who are they? In excerpt 2, 'it' is used but does not refer to an object earlier mentioned; it is a process, or a sequence of processes, grammatically a clause which is being transmuted into a report. This is special kind of it, which joins linguistic items. There is an ellipsis of nominal group in excerpt 2, where the word, 'money' in excerpt 2 is being ellipited... share of (money). Though the word is missing, yet, it recovable in the preceding excerpts. There is a lexical repetition of the word 'fifty-fifty' in excerpt 3. Though it is grammatically wrong, a link is achieved. The correct version of this construction is 'two equal halves' or 'fifty each' or just 'equally'.

ESSAY 3:

Excerpt 1: This was to no avail, as we were ordered to lie down with our faces buried on the ground by the fierce looking armed robbers.

Excerpt 2: They were armed with gun and other dangerous weapons.

Excerpt 3: I was lying on the floor shivering with fear, like a cat beaten by early morning rain.

Comment: There is a meaning inclusion between, 'gun' being a kind of 'weapon'. 'Gun' is a hyponym of 'weapon' which is the super ordinate.

A comparative reference is established by comparing the manner in which the speaker shivers and that of a cat.

ESSAY 5

Excerpt 1: My name is (name withheld), residing at Malam Inna in Tudun Wada, Gombe. I am year-two student of English at Gombe State University.

Comment: 'My' used above is a typical possessive construction which indicates some sort of relation that allows the reader/hearer to identify the 'possessive' entity by linking it to 'the possessor'.

ESSAY 6

Excerpt 1: I peeped to see who have been talking and found out their faces were strange. The quarrel started like a joke and it resulted into a serious fight.

Comment: There is a loose sense of synonym between, 'quarrel' and 'fight' which is obviously the reason for the link.

Excerpt 2: It was a beautiful evening. The heaven in its majestic splendour and the sky were adored with the flowing gleams.

Comment: Frequent use of 'the' as indicated above is associated with recognizable objects in the environment which is situational (exophoric). So, the referents are identified on extra linguistic ground. The reader/hearer needs not to suffer to relate the meaning because there exists only one kind of 'heaven' and 'sky'

ESSAY 7

Excerpt 1: I thought of shouting, but I thought that it might be armed robbers. I heard some one calling the other, Lion while the second one was called Tiger.

Comment: naming is used to make reference. When it is used, it draws the hearer's attention, or reminds one of the existence, or relevance of the person being named. It may also be used to warn, etc. In this excerpt, 'Lion and Tiger' are used to make reference to robbers in another clause. Therefore, a linguistic bond is established between the two distinct pairs of words, 'armed robbers' and 'Lion and Tiger'.

SUGGESTION ON HOW TO PROMOTE WRITING IN CLASSROOM

In Nigerian schools, some students feel that they are somehow writing in a vacuum. This feeling is reinforced by marking and grades are assigned which communicates to the students that marks are the only reason for writing, or they are obliged to write because they will have reproduce the message one day in examinations. This presupposes that a good writing earns high marks, or leads to passing examinations, and not one which communicates to the public.

To make writing more interactive, an awareness of audience has to be reinforced. By so doing, the student-writer is forced to consider the audience and is likely to adopt a reader-oriented approach to writing. The reader, or the examiner is not the only audience and should not be considered as either a critic or marks-giver. When the student-writer has a variety of audience in mind, it can lead to flexibility, control and mastering of this noble skill-writing.

The following are ways writing can be promoted.

1. Whole class discusses a given text for a different audience.
2. Two or more students work together to produce a single, agreed text.
3. Whole class composes short texts on the board.
4. Students exchange first draft of a text and point out to one another changes which may be necessary to help the reader understand the whole message.

5. Whole class examination of one or two texts with names and numbers removed, photocopied and distributed to the entire class.
6. Specification of a target audience for a text, and making it as real.

CONCLUSION

The power to interpret texts lies on their textuality. For this reason, analyzing text messages from cohesive viewpoint entails evaluating not only the linguistic characteristics of the text producers, the interpreting capability of the reader, but a general comprehension and criticism of text messages.

Though no one thinks, or behaves the same way always, it is astonishing to note that there is a kind of similarity among the writing styles of the students.

The essays do not manifest many connective features explained in this paper. Further more, most of the relationship established among the linguistic elements are never expressed in implied form- something that indicates the linguistic creativity and competence of the writer. Perhaps, this deficiency could be attributed to the inability of the writers to enrich their vocabularies. However, there are coherence and cohesion in all the essays.

Text analysts should realize the significance of contexts in social domain such as education, politics, legislation, teaching, etc. Cognitive properties of the text participants such as their aims, beliefs, and knowledge play important roles in that they assist in explaining why people write in particular ways. This is the reason why understanding a discourse should not be limited to isolated sentences but it should be studied from as an integrated part of processing with production and consumption playing key roles. So, a text in a discourse is considered to be coherent if it has a mental model.

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